

THE COMPETENCE APPROACH IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS FOREIGN IN FERGHANA STATE UNIVERSITY

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ABSTRACT

The article deals with the peculiarities of competence approach in education, and also examines the application of this approach in teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Today, the competence approach in education is opposed to the ZUNOVSKY and qualification approach to determining goals, results and, accordingly, standards of higher professional education. It involves the development of a quality assurance system for the training of future specialists that meets the needs of the modern world labor market.

It should be noted that the competence approach is opposed to "knowledge" in the sense of transferring ready-made knowledge to students in the form of information, information.

The units of the competence approach are competence and competence. Competence is a set of professional and personal qualities that ensure the effective implementation of competencies.

The use of a competence-based approach in the course of training specialists leads to the formation of a certain set of key

competencies among trainees, the implementation of which will allow them (trainees) to successfully socialize. Unlike the term "qualification", competencies include, in addition to specific professional knowledge and skills that characterize qualifications, qualities such as initiative, willingness to cooperate, ability to work in a group, communication skills, the ability to learn, evaluate, think logically, select and use information. From the standpoint of the competence approach, the level of education is determined by the ability to solve problematic problems of varying complexity on the basis of existing knowledge, and more significant and effective for successful professional activity are not scattered knowledge, but generalized skills, manifested in the willingness to solve life and professional problems, the ability to communicate in a foreign language, training in information

technology, etc. Competence can be defined as a set of abilities to realize one's potential (knowledge, skills, experience) for successful creative activity, taking into account the understanding of the problem, the presentation of the predicted results, the disclosure of the causes that complicate the activity, the proposal of means to eliminate these causes, the implementation of necessary actions and evaluation of the predicted results. In this interpretation of competence, it is not the awareness of students that is put forward in the first place, but the ability to solve problems.

The introduction of a competence-based approach to the educational process requires serious changes in the content of education, in the implementation of the educational process, and in the practice of the teacher.

The use of a competence-based approach in teaching Russian as a foreign language contributes to the formation of professional skills necessary for a future specialist, provided for by qualification characteristics. The main purpose of the training is to teach students the Russian language as a real means of communication between specialists from different countries and at the same time representatives of different linguistic and cultural communities. Within the framework of this approach, the task of mastering language as a means of communication in real life situations becomes urgent.

Until recently, two main methods were used in the process of teaching foreign languages — translation-grammatical and direct. In search of a new method, many of our methodologists and teachers again turn to the principles of "straightforwardness", at the same time striving to base the

teaching on the data of modern structural linguistics. Along with this, there is a desire to implement a consciously practical method in teaching a foreign language. A distinctive feature of this method is the practical assimilation by students of lexical, grammatical and phonetic features of foreign language speech based on their conscious understanding. Foreign language and speech practice is considered to be the decisive factor of learning, but it is based on language theory. The latter should be given no more than 15-20% of the study time. The presence of consciousness with this method ensures the fastest, easiest and most durable assimilation of a foreign language, and speech practice contributes to the development of foreign language thinking among students. Since language is closely connected with thinking, practical language proficiency is impossible without the ability to think in it, therefore thinking in a foreign language is considered as the main foreign language-speech ability, which is always brought up or developed by students in the process of learning a foreign language.

Today, the first place among the methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language belongs to the communicative method (the name was proposed by E.I. Passov). Its purpose is to develop students' skills to solve communicative tasks by means of a foreign language, to communicate freely with its native speakers. Thus, the language is learned during natural communication, the organizer and participant of which is the teacher. At the same time, the student performs the role of the subject of this communication and must constantly act.

This area of methodological research is developing under the significant influence of communicative linguistics and its

qualities such as communicativeness, consistency, functionality are considered as the main properties of the studied language.

Russian teaching as a foreign language from the point of view of the competence approach, we can talk about the need to move from the translation-grammatical and conscious-practical methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language to the communicative method of language acquisition.

At the Fergana State University, the competence approach in teaching Russian as a foreign language is implemented in a modular learning system, while the module is understood as a unit of discipline content.

The content of training, based on the principles of modularity, creates conditions for cyclical management of the educational process and, ultimately, for achieving the goals put forward.

Russian as a Foreign language has been compiled by the university teachers on the basis of the state educational standard, on the basis of which a new textbook is being developed by the teacher of the Russian Language Methodology Department.

The manual does not have an after-school development, which will make its structure

flexible and give the teacher the opportunity to choose certain topics taking into account the needs, personal characteristics and interests of a specific contingent of students.

Modular teaching of Russian as a foreign language to students provides flexibility of content, adaptation to individual needs of the individual and the level of her training through the organization of educational and cognitive activities according to an individual curriculum. Thus, it becomes possible to plan and implement an individual educational trajectory. Nonlinear trajectories in the organization of the educational process are a necessary element of the student-centered learning model.

The implementation of a competence-based approach in teaching Russian as a foreign language at a university contributes to the achievement of its main goal - the training of a qualified specialist of the appropriate level and profile, competitive in the labor market, fluent in his profession and oriented in related fields of activity, capable of effective work in the specialty at the level of world standards, ready for continuous professional growth, social and professional mobility.

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